

Animals, plants, cancer cells and microbes know all facts about the center of earth

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(Dated: October 31, 2020)

Up to date, scientific communities believed that center of earth is a hot metal core which its evolutions causes to going hot matters from volcanoes or the emergency of earthquakes. However, this model couldn't response to many questions in biology and life. We suggest a model that replace a hot metal core with a very compact biological system. To clear this point, we should go some steps higher and propose a new model which considers evolutions of biosystems and cosmology with together. 1. This model unifies biology with cosmology in a unified biocosmology theory and considers evolutions of biocosmic system from big bang to present. 2. In this model, a point decays into several closed strings. 3. Some closed strings join to each other and form space, time and some branes. Our universe is born on the connected region of two branes. One brane and its fields are observable and another brane and its fields are hidden. However, their signatures could be observed. For example, the velocity of exchanging information between spinors is faster than velocity of light and this may be done by hidden waves in hidden branes. 4. Some other closed strings decay into open strings and produce particles, planets and other matters. 5. Some closed strings decay into three types of biological systems, one within the center of planets like earth, one on the planets and another in other hidden brane. 6. Summing over genes within the center of planets, on the planets and in other hidden brane should be a constant number related to a closed string. 7. According to this law, by passing time and increasing number of creatures on the earth, their size should become smaller such as total number of genes in system be a constant. This is in agreement with what we see in history of evolutions of life and the size of creatures on the earth. 8. In this model, compacting of biological structure within the center of earth cause to the emergency of hot temperature and emergency of gravitational waves. We can re-obtain all known physics of earth like its gravity, earthquakes and volcanoes in this model. 9. In addition to known exchanged forces like gravity and electromagnetic ones, there are some extra waves in hidden brane which couldn't be observed in our universe, however their signatures could be observed; for example in Pauli's repulsive principle. The biological system within the center of earth uses of these waves to control DNA/RNAs and other elements of life. For this reason, linear electronic devices like those in hands of human couldn't detect these waves. 10. This system exchange waves with neural systems of animals and consequently, they could predict the earthquake. 11. This system determine the behaviour of plants in different seasons and cause to some changes in color of leaves. 12. This system communicates with cancer cells and increase or decrease their growth. For this reason, in space stations, we observe a change in the growth of tumours. Also, this system communicates with microbes and controls their growth. This is in agreement with observations in space stations. 13. Comparing this system with biological system within the cells, we can find new origins for some strategic gases like Methane and also oil. Because, this genetic structure evolves and repels or absorbs CH_3 . This molecule combines with other molecules and produce CH_4 and other main economical molecules. 14. Finally, biological center of earth emit different waves in different points of earth which causes to the emergence of different human's faces.

PACS numbers: 73.20.-r, 73.22.-f, 04.62.+v

Keywords: Biology; Cosmology; Earth; String theory; Microbes; Plants; Animals

I. INTRODUCTION

Up to date, cosmologists worked only on black holes, stars, planets and physical laws. On the other hand, biologists only investigated about evolutions of microbes, animals, plants and human. These two groups of scientists propose very great models in their expertises, however, when they confront a problem in connected region of these two fields of science, usually stop. However, there are many questions which we couldn't response them in cosmology or biology alone and we need to a generalized model which unifies both cosmology and biology. For example, many investigations have been done on the evolutions of dinosaurs from their birth, growth and finally disappearance [1–4]. Now, the

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question arises that why dinosaurs were so big in early stages of the earth and creatures after them like some lizards are so small? Maybe, some scientists have tried to response this question, however, most of these responses couldnt be convince able.

Another main question is that why faces of human varies from a point to another on the earth. For example, why Chinese people have different faces respect to European ones or why color of skin in Africa is different from other points of the world? To response these questions, many investigations have been done on the evolutionary History of Human Skin Pigmentation (See for example [5–8]). Some of these articles about the genetic origin of these differences; however, one could ask that what is the reason for differences in human’s genes? Thus, we need to a model which give more reasoning descriptions.

On the other hand, some experiments show that the growth of tumorous and cancer cells could be stopped or decreased within the international space stations or under microgravity conditions [9, 10]. Also, some experiments indicate that growth and interaction of microbes in a shuttle or a space station is different from their growth and interactions on the earth [11, 12]. Some scientists have tried to describe these events by using concepts of microgravity; however, how we can connect genetic evolutions to gravity, microgravity and other waves? To response these questions, we have to propose a new model which makes a bridge between cosmology and biology. This models should consider the evolutions of bio-cosmos from big bang to present era. This model also suggest a new structure for the core of earth. This model not only confirms all known physics about earth but also discusses about the origin of life in the context of some main theories like string theory and M-theory [13, 14].

The outline of this paper is as follows: In section II, we build a bio-cosmological model and introduce some laws. In section III, using this theoretical model, we response to present questions in connected bridges between biology and physics.

II. LAWS IN BIO-COSMOLOGY MODEL

In this bio-cosmic model, a point-like object could decay topologically into three types of closed strings (See figure 1). Some closed strings form branes, some others build matters, anti-matters and planets and third ones build biological genes, proteins and et al. First group of closed strings join to each other and form space-time dimensions and branes (See figure 2). For example, a 1-dimensional brane should be produced by joining two closed strings. A 2-dimensional brane could be emerged by joining three closed strings. And totally, a N-dimensional brane could be created by joining N+1 closed strings. Our universe is located on the connected region of two branes. One of branes and its particles and fields are observable and could be seen by our eyes. In this brane, some strings play the role of photons or gravitons. Also, one end of some strings are located on this brane and produce charged particles like electrons and positrons. Besides these observable fields and particles, there are some strings which live on the hidden brane. These strings produce some waves and particles that we couldnt see. For example, some closed strings may produce huge repulsive force between two parallel spinors like two parallel electrons. For this reason, when you change spin of electron in one side of a universe, spin of other electron in other side of universe should be changed. The communications between spinors is very fast even faster velocity of light. Thus, we can guess that the origin of repulsive force in Pauli principle could be hidden waves which live in hidden brane (See figure 3).

Third type of closed strings decay into three types of biological matters. One type of biological genes lives on the planets, second type is placed within the center of planets and other type lives on the hidden brane. By combining three types of genetic matters, their compacting and coiling become open and they shrink topologically to a closed string (See figure 4).

Now the question arises that how this model confirms the observations like hot temperature within the center of earth or gravitational force between planets. To response this question, we should reconsider the structure of DNAs. A DNA is formed from hexagonal and pentagonal molecules. These molecules are formed from charged electrons and atoms. By compacting a DNA, its parallel electrons become closed to each other and a huge repulsive force is emerged. If length of this DNA be 10^9 times of the center of earth, number of couplings between parallel spins increase and repulsive force increase. Also, by increasing mass and charges, two gravitational and electromagnetic forces increase so. These forces produces huge acceleration. According to equivalence principle [15], this acceleration has a direct relation with temperature and cause to its increase:

$$T_{center-earth} \sim \frac{a_{particles-within-center}}{2\pi} \sim \frac{F_{repulsive} + F_{gravity} + F_{electromagnetic} + \dots}{2\pi} \quad (1)$$

where $T_{center-earth}$ is the temperature of earth, a is the acceleration of system, $F_{repulsive}$ is the force between parallel spins, $F_{gravity}$ is the gravitational force and $F_{electromagnetic}$ is the force between electrical charges. These forces cause to the acceleration of particles and emergence of hot temperature. This temperature causes to movement

FIG. 1: A point could decay into three types of closed strings related to biological matters, cosmic matters and cosmic space-time

FIG. 2: By joining $N+1$ closed strings, N dimensional branes are born.

of some hot gases and liquids from center to the surface of the earth and confirm the evolutions of volcanoes (See figure 5).

On the other hand, summing over masses of genes within the center of earth could be equal to predicted mass of core and produce the same gravitational force on the planet.

$$F_{gravity-surface} = G \frac{m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n}{r} = G \frac{M}{r} \quad (2)$$

FIG. 3: Our universe lives on the connected region of two branes. One of branes is observable and other one is hidden. Fields which live on hidden brane couldn't be seen; however their effects could be observed.

Above equation shows that for an observer which live on the planet, the gravitational force which is emerged by genetic center within the earth is equal to the force which is produced by an equal mass within the core. Thus, this model gives the same physics of a hot massive metal core within the center of earth (See figure 5).

FIG. 4: A biological closed string decays into three types of biological matters, one which lives on the planets, second which lives within the center of planets and third which is located on hidden brane

Summing over topologies of three types of genes within the center of planets, on the planets and in hidden branes should produce a closed string. Thus, we can write a law for this system (See figure 6).

$$\begin{aligned}
 Constant &= \text{Total Number of genes} = \\
 &= \text{Number of genes on the planets (M)} + \\
 &= \text{Number of genes within the center of planets (N)} + \\
 &= \text{Number of genes in hidden branes (L)}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3}$$

FIG. 5: A biological object is compacted within the center of earth and produce the same temperature and gravity of a hot metal core.

This is very main law in bio-cosmology. This law helps us to discover the reason for changing size of creatures by passing time. As we know in initial stages of earth's life, there were big animals like dinosaurs, while by passing time, size of creatures decrease and some animals like lizards are emerged. We can write (See figure 7):

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\text{Number of genes on the planets (M)} = \\
 &\text{Number of creatures} \otimes \text{Number of genes within each creature} \quad (4)
 \end{aligned}$$

Above equation shows that for stability in number of total genes, by increasing number of creatures, number of their genes should be reduced. This causes that number of cells decrease and creatures become smaller. This is in agreement with observations.

FIG. 6: Summing over number of genes on the planets, within the center of planets and on the other brane should be a constant.

III. ANSWER TO QUESTIONS IN THE BIO-COSMOLOGY MODEL

Now, we can answer some questions. For example, one can ask why animals could predict earthquakes? To answer this question, we should accept that the neural system within the brain can communicate with biological center within the earth and detect its evolutions. Each gene has several functions and for each of these functions, a circuit is emerged in a brain. Thus, any gene is in direct relation with several circuits within a brain. This means that genetic center within the center of earth is related to some neural circuits within a brain. Thus, a brain can understand

FIG. 7: To keep number of genes constant, by passing time and increasing number of creatures, their sizes should become smaller.

evolutions of earth. Animals have more focuses than human, because human should think about different problems however animals have less problems to solve. For this reason, their neurons could detect more signals from the earth's center. Also, some neural circuits could detect signals of genes in hidden branes (See figure 8). Thus, a brain could see 11-dimensional world and analyse its evolutions.

FIG. 8: A brain includes some neural circuits which analyse evolutions within the center of earth and hidden brane.

In addition to animals, microbes and cancer cells also communicate waves with the biological center of earth. In fact, the biological center of earth control the growth of cells and microbes. However, by increasing separation distance between biological center of earth and cells or microbes, they couldnt exchange any wave and this control is disappeared. For this reason, we observe that the growth of tumors in space stations is stopped or growth of some microbes increase suddenly (See figure 9).

The biological center of earth plays the main role in changing color of leaves and life of plants during different seasons. There are several color pigments within a leaf like chlorophyll which produce green color, carotene which is the main cause of yellow color and other ones. By closing autumn, the biological center of earth send a message to the plant and order for transferring Mg from chlorophyll and leaves to roots and changing color of leaves. This is in agreement with observations (See figure 10).

If this model be true, we can use of it to determine the place and origin of economical gases like methane and also some oils. A DNA could absorb or repel methyl groups like CH_3 . This molecule could combine with hydrogen and produce CH_4 . Then this molecule could go out of center of earth, achieve to surface and be taken by drilling

FIG. 9: Evolutions of cancer cells and microbes are controlled by earth's waves and by reducing these waves, their growths decrease or increase suddenly.

FIG. 10: The biological center within the earth communicates with cells within plants, inform them about changes in seasons and program their new colors.

platforms or volcanoes. Although, some of these gases may be covered by soil and oil and don't come out of earth. This theory may change economy of world (See Figure 11).

Finally, using this model, we answer to a main question. Why human's face is changed in different points of universe? For example, Chinese people have different faces respect to European people. If we accept that our model is true, then, we can conclude that there are different genes within the center of earth. Each point on the surface is closed to some types of genes and consequently, waves of these genes are more effective in creation of animals, plants and human. For this reason, in each point of universe, we observe special types of animals, plants and human faces (See Figure 12).

FIG. 11: The biological center within the earth repel some CH_3S . These molecules combine with hydrogen and produce methane. This gas could be found in volcanoes or by drilling platforms.

FIG. 12: The biological center within the earth control face and shape of creatures and human in different points of earth.

IV. CONCLUSION:

Present theories about the origin of universe and life couldn't be unified and couldn't response to our questions. For example, why creatures become smaller by passing time. Or why animals could predict earthquakes. We propose a model which unifies biology with cosmology in a unified bio-cosmic model. In this model, a point decay into some closed strings. Some strings build cosmic space-times and branes. Some others form particles, matters and anti-matters. Other ones build biological matters within the planets, on planets and on other branes. Number of genes in these three systems should be a constant. This means that by increasing number of creatures, their sizes should be reduced. This is in agreement with observations on the earth which shows initial animals were big. On the other hand, this model rebuild physics of earth and universe and gives all known properties. In this model, in addition to

known waves like gravity and electromagnetic fields, there are some waves which couldn't be observed however their effects could be seen. Genetic matters within the planets, on planets and in other brane communicate with each other through these waves. This communication help to animal to predict earthquake. Also, using these waves, plants understand change of season and their color is changed. In addition, without these waves, microbes grow without control as we can see in some experiments which be done distant of earth in space stations. On the other hand, the biological system within the center of earth acts like cells, produce some CH_3 s. These molecules combine with other hydrogen and molecules and produce CH_4 s. Thus, the origin of economical gases could be also the biological system within the center of earth. Finally, one can assert that earth's waves determine faces of human in different points of earth. For this reason, we observe different faces for chines, African, European and other people.

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Author Contribution statement

Contributions of all authors are the same.